

Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution and Minimization of Information Versus Extremization Part 2

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In Part 1, we noted that Shannon's entropy is often maximized with respect to the constraint $\sum_i p(e_i) e_i = E_{\text{total}}$ to obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. Maximization (or extremization) is a well-known math procedure. In Part 1, we suggested that due to properties of probabilities in AND situations (i.e. $p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_1+e_2)$ no normalization), one has two additive quantities in the problem, namely e_i and $\ln(p(e_i))$. We then argued that to have the minimal informational solution, $\ln(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$, where $-1/T$ is a constant.

Here we wish to elaborate on this idea. We suggest that in order to maximize a function which arises a priori, e.g. Shannon's entropy - $\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$, one must incorporate all necessary constraints. Certainly $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{\text{total}}$ is an obvious constraint, but we suggest that the AND property of probability actually leads to a second constraint, namely that $\ln(p(e_i)) = \text{constant} * e_i$. This is a constraint, not a result of maximization, and it must be implemented before maximization occurs. The point, however, is that $\ln(p(e_i)) = \text{constant} * e_i$ solves for the distribution (Maxwell-Boltzmann $C \exp(-e_i/T)$) without any maximization being necessary. We argue that $\ln(p(e_i)) = \text{constant} * e_i$ follows not from minimal informational suggestions made in Part 1, but from math. Thus, a constraint in the problem actually solves the problem, we suggest.

Shannon's Entropy and Extremization

Shannon's entropy - $\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ may be maximized subject to the constraint $\sum_i p(e_i) e_i = E_{\text{total}}$ to yield the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$, as is well-known. In Part 1, we showed that Shannon's entropy arises from calculating:

$$\text{Probability}(N \rightarrow \text{infinite runs}) = 1 / \text{number of states} = \text{Product over } i p(e_i)^{N p(e_i)} \quad ((1))$$

Here it is assumed that if N is very large, $N p(e_i) = n(e_i) = \text{number of independent } e_i\text{'s}$.

The strategy maintained in the literature is that one wishes to have as many states as possible because any restriction represents a bias and one assumes that no such bias exists. This leads to the mathematical maximization of $-\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ subject to the a priori constraint $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{\text{total}}$ and yields the MB distribution.

The problem with this approach, we argue, is that $\sum_i p(e_i) e_i$ is not the only a priori constraint in the problem. Formally, one must include all relevant constraints and a second fundamental constraint exists. This constraint must be included before one may consider performing the maximization process, we argue.

A Second Constraint Due to the Properties of Probability

In Part 1, we argued that probability must adhere to the AND condition, i.e.

$$p(e_i) p(e_j) = p(e_i + e_j) \text{ for } p(e_i) \text{ unnormalized } ((2))$$

$\ln(p(e_i))$ is an additive quantity, just as e_i is an additive quantity, as we pointed out in Part 1.

The question becomes: Is it possible to determine the functional form of $p(e_i)$ based on ((2))?

$p(e_i)$ is a function of e_i . A solution to ((2)) is:

$$p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T) ((3))$$

Thus, the probability property or constraint ((2)) does lead to a possible solution for $p(e_i)$ without any notion of maximization. We argue that this solution is representative of the second constraint ((3)) and must be considered before any maximization process is employed.

Thus, we argue that one cannot formally maximize:

$$- \text{Sum over } i \ p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) + \text{constant Sum over } i \ e_i p(e_i) ((5))$$

without first associating $\ln(p(e_i))$ with constant * e_i (e.g. $-e_i/T$). This, however, means that the a priori Shannon's entropy function is really:

$$- \text{Sum over } i \ e_i p(e_i) ((6))$$

and so there is nothing to maximize. We thus suggest that it is formally invalid to maximize Shannon's entropy subject to $\text{Sum over } i \ e_i p(e_i)$, ignoring $\ln(p(e_i)) = \text{constant} * e_i$ which is a valid constraint which must first be utilized. Utilizing it, however, yields the solution to the problem, $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$, without any maximization required. We thus question why one maximizes Shannon's entropy subject to the constraint $\text{Sum over } i \ p(e_i) e_i = E$ total instead of writing $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ from the probability constraint ((2)).

Conclusion

In conclusion, the maximization/extremization of a function subject to necessary constraints is a very useful math procedure which is often employed in physics. We also note, as shown in Part 1, that one may derive:

$$1/\text{number of states} = \exp(\text{Sum over } i \ p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))) \text{ for } N \rightarrow \text{infinite.}$$

In other words, $\ln(\text{number of states}) = -\text{Sum over } i \ p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$. One may then legitimately argue that one should maximize this value subject to constraints which exist. An obvious

constraint is $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{\text{total}}$ and one usually proceeds with the maximization to obtain $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$.

We argue here, however, that a second necessary constraint holds which follows from the AND features of probability, i.e. $p(e_i) p(e_j) = p(e_i + e_j)$, where $p(e_i)$ is unnormalized. This constraint, however, immediately leads to the solution $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$. Furthermore, the constraint, which follows from basic AND probability behaviour, must apply, it cannot be discarded. Thus, we argue that it must be applied to the a priori Shannon's entropy expression, $-\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ before any maximization occurs. This second constraint, however, already solves the problem and so there is no maximization to be performed as argued in Part 1.